

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

Towards an attractive and inclusive European Research Area (ERA): Removing legal and administrative barriers for mobile researchers in Europe

The Marie Curie Alumni Association ([MCAA](#)) and the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers ([Eurodoc](#)) believe that the upcoming ERA Act is a crucial opportunity to address systemic challenges and make the European Union (EU) an inclusive, fair, and secure environment for researchers. Among these challenges, legal and administrative barriers, such as burdensome visa procedures and the difficulty in recognising scientific career structures, continue to limit researchers' mobility and work opportunities. These barriers undermine the EU's attractiveness, despite recent initiatives such as Choose Europe for Science. Addressing them is therefore essential to unlock the full potential of the ERA and ensure that researchers can fully benefit from it, at every career stage and regardless of their origin.

This statement draws on data collected through:

- A comprehensive survey was conducted within the project "[MCAA New Horizon: Enhancing the impact of MSCA Alumni on the European Research Landscape](#)." The survey was designed to gather detailed insights into the challenges faced by MSCA fellows (both MCAA members and non-members), such as visa issues, salary transparency, and administrative hurdles, providing a nuanced understanding of the areas where improvements are needed. Data were collected over a 16-week period, from 15 March to 5 July 2024, and a total of approximately 1,200 valid responses were received.
- An MCAA membership survey, conducted in 2022, which evaluated the impact and reach of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions ([MSCA](#)) and addressed pertinent issues that MCAA members face both during their MSCA fellowship and beyond. The survey was conducted from March to December 2022, and a total of 1,185 valid responses were received.

The key results of the survey are described in the following sections.

Addressing visa and residence permit requirements

While EU Directive 2016/801 provides a legal framework for the conditions of entry and residence of third-country nationals for the purposes of research, studies, and training, challenges related to visa and residency requirements remain. These

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

challenges have been highlighted by the MSCA community for both recruitment and project implementation phases.

According to the data collected in the MCAA survey in 2024, 25.3% of respondents reported a lack of clarity and comprehensibility of the paperwork involved in their recruitment process. Moreover, visa-related issues appeared particularly challenging for MSCA fellows, with only 55.1% of respondents rating the clarity of communication regarding visas as "good" or "very good" for both non-EU nationals conducting their research in an EU country and for EU nationals carrying out their research in a non-EU country. However, some significant differences appeared between the two categories.

Approximately 60% of EU fellows reported that they did not encounter significant immigration or residence issues during their time in a non-EU country. However, more than one-fifth highlighted difficulties with immigration procedures and mobility, suggesting that while many benefitted from the support provided by their host institutions regarding visa and residence permits, a notable minority experienced hurdles that may have impacted their overall experience.

On the other hand, non-EU citizens in the EU reported a higher prevalence of immigration-related challenges, with 38.3% acknowledging that they faced issues during their research stay. This figure starkly contrasts with the 21.8% of EU citizens who experienced similar problems while abroad. Additionally, more than 30% of non-EU respondents indicated that these immigration issues limited their mobility (compared to 20.5% of EU citizens experiencing the same situation in non-EU countries), illustrating the additional obstacles for researchers from outside the EU when integrating into the European academic landscape. These results sharpen the MORE4¹ report finding that immigration rules disproportionately hinder non-EU researchers.²

Together with the ERA Act, the upcoming visa strategy as part of the union of skills represents a key opportunity to strengthen researchers' mobility across Europe, while addressing current visa and residency challenges. It would make the EU a more open and competitive research environment, and enhance its attractiveness through the implementation of mobility schemes such as the MSCA Choose Europe for Science pilot action.

¹ MORE4 – *Support data collection and analysis concerning mobility patterns and career paths of researchers* – Annexes to the final report, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/56007>

² For non-EU researchers wanting to come back to Europe, key barriers include: visa/work permits (34%), transfer of pensions (72%), social security entitlements (70%).

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

Advancing contractual transparency and onboarding support

Researchers' onboarding experiences vary significantly across institutions based on their nationality and the location of their MSCA fellowship. According to the data collected in the 2024 MCAA survey, 30% of respondents felt that the support provided by host institutions during the onboarding process was fair to poor, and 40% of them evaluated the mentorship they received similarly.

This is particularly evident in the evaluation of support for personal matters, such as housing and assistance for dependents and family members (e.g., dual-career support). In these areas, more than 50% of respondents rate the support as fair or poor, with important differences between EU nationals' fellowships in non-EU countries and those of non-EU citizens in EU countries. These data echo the MORE4 evidence from 2021, which found that logistics were listed as a barrier for mobility among 54.4% of non-mobile PhD candidates (up from 28.8% in 2016) and among 61% of non-mobile post-PhD researchers.

Contractual transparency is also one of the cornerstones of researchers' well-being and research career attractiveness. In this sense, income levels and clarity of tax declaration procedures in the host country are important indicators that can affect both researchers and their families. While just over 50% of EU citizens conducting their MSCA fellowship in a non-EU country believed their salary was sufficient to cover basic necessities, such as health insurance, according to the survey, less than 20% reported that their salaries were adequate to support bringing their family with them. This new evidence provides insights into the MORE4 findings, which identified that family reasons tend to dominate among mobility barriers (78–79% of non-mobile PhDs and post-PhDs). Additionally, only 50% of them reported that they were not sufficiently informed by their host institution about tax declaration matters. Non-EU citizens conducting their MSCA research in EU countries have a different perspective, with 77% of survey respondents believing that their salary was sufficient to cover basic necessities, such as health insurance, and 41.2% reporting that their salaries were adequate to support bringing their family with them. The same observation was made for tax declaration procedures, where 37.8% of non-EU fellows felt the tax procedures were clearly explained and 41.3% disagreed.

Regarding housing support, data from the MCAA 2024 survey highlight a similar situation for both EU citizens conducting their MSCA fellowship in a non-EU country

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

(33.3%) and non-EU citizens carrying out their MSCA research in EU countries (38.1%), with both groups reporting difficulties in arranging housing.

To this end, **standardised practices could ensure fair and transparent integration of researchers, while fostering mobility.** Introducing a European contract template, in line with the EU Charter for Researchers and respecting the division of competence between the EU and Member States, would improve recruitment processes. Moreover, identifying minimum mandatory contractual standards, inspired by the approach taken in Directive 1999/70/EC³ on fixed-term work, would help reduce precarious employment practices and strengthen legal certainty. Combined with improved access to social protection and health security, this would also make researchers' mobility accessible, inclusive, and attractive for both researchers and their families.

Enhancing career progression through the R1–R4 framework

The European Framework for Research Careers provides a structured understanding of career stages (R1–R4) across sectors in Europe. While most MSCA fellows value the positive impact of the MSCA fellowship on their career perspectives, the 2022 MCAA survey underlines some discrepancies between sectors in terms of employability.

According to the collected data, 51% of respondents reported that the MSCA fellowship had a significant impact on their employability in academia, while 34% indicated a moderate improvement. Employment prospects in industry were also perceived as enhanced following the fellowship, with 36% of respondents reporting a slight improvement in employability and 16% a significant improvement. Other sectors, such as public administration, entrepreneurship, and non-profit, were largely regarded as unknown or irrelevant to the MSCA project.

The European Framework for Research Careers was established to provide a structured, common reference point for researchers across all sectors, fostering cross-border and cross-sector mobility. However, this structure is not widely and uniformly understood or recognised across Member States and institutions. The survey data underlined that high-quality training doesn't necessarily mean employability without harmonised and structured career frameworks. Introducing a

³ Council Directive 1999/70/EC from 28 June 1999 concerning the framework agreement on fixed-term work concluded by ETUC, UNICE and CEEP.

<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1999/70/1999-07-10>

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

binding requirement to the R1–R4 framework to map institutional and national career structures and using these profiles in vacancy announcements would help formalise recognition of research experience, clarify eligibility criteria, and provide transparency in career progression. Such measures could reduce fragmentation, improve employability, and foster mobility across academia, industry, public administration, and non-profit sectors.

In addition to the survey, both the MCAA and Eurodoc held multiple consultations with researchers from different career stages to understand their challenges. Apart from the challenges mentioned above, several other issues were critical for mobile researchers. For example, the lack of a standardised contract framework for researchers across Europe creates significant issues. Contracts are often drafted exclusively in the local language, making it challenging for a newly arrived researcher to fully understand their terms and conditions, including rights, responsibilities, and career prospects. This absence of common minimum standards for research contracts is a known structural obstacle to good working conditions. The issue is compounded by a broader linguistic challenge, where differing communities of practice and national jargon create conflicts in implementing EU-wide standards and policies. Finally, it is also worth noting that the above issues are often compounded. For example, low salaries or a lack of dedicated financial support for mobility exacerbate the typical costs associated with mobility, such as visa and residence permit fees, as well as health insurance.

To resolve the above issues and fully realise the potential of the ERA, the MCAA & Eurodoc commend:

- **Enforce and enhance the scientific visa directive:** Ensure full and consistent implementation of Directive (EU) 2016/801 for both third-country and European researchers. Prioritise faster procedures and improved mobility.
- **Establish a European researcher contract standard:** Mandate the development and adoption of a common minimum standard for research contracts across the ERA, which should be provided in two versions: a version in the local language, which may most likely be the legally valid version, and version sworn translated in a widely spoken official EU language (most preferably English, given that it is EU's preferred language for the submission of research proposals) to ensure transparency and clarity for mobile researchers.

Statement by the MCAA & Eurodoc on researcher mobility

- **Mandate the use of R1–R4 in recruitment:** Require that all national vacancy announcements for research positions specify the corresponding R1–R4 profile, standardising eligibility criteria and increasing career transparency across borders and sectors. Introduce a binding legislative requirement for all public and publicly-funded institutions to formally map their national and institutional career structures, job titles, and pay scales to the R1–R4 European Framework for Research Careers.
- **Accelerate qualification recognition procedures:** Introduce measures within the ERA Act to simplify and accelerate the automatic or semi-automatic professional recognition of foreign research degrees and qualifications across Member States for public employment, ensuring the principles of the Lisbon Recognition Convention are swiftly and effectively applied.

About this statement

This statement was approved by the Board of Eurodoc 2025/2026 on the 14.11.2025

This statement was approved by the MCAA Executive Committee 2024/2026 on the 14.11.2025

List of authors

- Nicolas Defaye, [0009-0008-0931-4993](#)
- Tereza Simova, [0000-0002-1774-4335](#)
- Gian Maria Greco, [0000-0002-8714-6349](#)
- Nicola Dengo, [0000-0003-2534-7265](#)
- Karl Kilbo Edlund, [0000-0001-7586-4119](#)
- Norbert Bencze, [0000-0001-7108-5329](#)
- Aleksandra Joanna Lewandowska, [0000-0002-7762-2890](#)
- Mostafa Moonir Shawrav, [0000-0001-8639-0393](#)

Date of publication: 14.11.2025

Contact: Eurodoc Board board@eurodoc.net and the MCAA contact@mariecuriealumni.eu

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17608024

Eurodoc, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, is a grassroots federation of 26 national associations of early-career researchers (ECRs) from 25 countries across Europe. Eurodoc was established 2002 and is based in Brussels. As a representative of doctoral candidates and junior researchers at the European level, Eurodoc engages with all major stakeholders in research, higher education, and innovation in Europe.

The Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA) is a global network of researchers who benefit or have benefited from the Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions (MSCA). The MCAA supports and contributes to the advancement of knowledge for a global, diverse, and informed society. The main focus of the MCAA is to promote career development and offer networking opportunities to its members, and contribute to shaping research and innovation policy. The MCAA currently has over 23,000 members from more than 150 countries, representing all career stages and diverse research fields. MCAA has over 35 geographical Chapters and more than 10 thematic Working Groups.